

CONFERENCE REPORT
10TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE NICHE TOURISM
26-28th JUNE 2019, DA NANG, VIETNAM
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The conference was attended by 80 delegates from 30 countries. Speakers of international standing gathered in Da Nang to identify and debate the latest issues and suggest strategies in the planning, development, marketing and management of Niche Tourism. The keynote speakers featured Professor Carlos Costa, University of Aveiro, Portugal and Professor Huong T. Bui, Ritsumeikan, Asian Pacific University, Japan who discussed tourism potential to boost local development and the socio-ecological systems approach to managing tourism in a living heritage site, respectively. There was a range of symposia, plenary sessions, oral presentations arranged in the two research-packed days. Delegates presented a range of interesting and thought-provoking papers on: Vortex Tourism, Heritage Tourism, Homestay Tourism, Environmental Sustainability Tourism, Marine Wildlife Tourism, Tea tourism to mention a few. The conference venue was the very impressive Novotel Conference Centre overlooking the Da Nang River and its intelligent design, colourful bridges. The conference hospitality included an exquisite cuisine of local delicacies and beverages at the conference where delegates had the opportunity to network in an informal and relaxed atmosphere.

The conference tours included day trips to Bana Hills and Cham Island. The trip to Bana Hills included a cable car ascent to 1000 m, a walk on the world-famous Golden Bridge, and a further ascent to the highest point of 1485 m Buddhist temple surrounded by tropical gardens and offering amazing far reaching views of Da Nang and the Vietnamese coastline. The trip to Cham Island included a snorkelling experience of the coral reef alongside a boat transfer to and from the island, a guided tour and a most delicious lunch followed by a much-deserved relaxation on the island's sandy beach under the shade of coconut trees. Groups of delegates took a trip to Hoi Ann, the traditional Vietnamese model town about an hour from Da Nang and experienced the local atmosphere of a UNESCO heritage site. The guided tours formed unforgettable experiences and acted as catalysts for generating new friendships and networking opportunities.

The city of Da Nang has a lot to offer to the visitor. From a safe stroll along the Dragon Bridge watching the dragon breathing fire on Saturday night to the most interesting Museum showing artefacts of the Chum Dynasty to the outstanding food at Madam Lang's busy restaurant and the lovely people of Vietnam. As a delegate I had a wonderful experience in Da Nang and was impressed by the quality of the conference outputs. I hope to see friends and colleagues at the forthcoming conference on *Sustainable Tourism, Culture and Sports 15-17 April 2020, Kathmandu, Nepal*. Special thanks to the conference organisers, Professor Eugenia Wickens, Dr Ali Bakir, Dr Vasiliki Avgeli, and Ian Wickens for making this experience possible.